

Towards densely sampled ultra-large area multi-MHz-OCT for *in vivo* skin measurements beyond 1 cm²/sec

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Abstract: We demonstrate a 3.3 MHz A-scan rate OCT for rapid scanning of large areas of human skin. The mosaicking performance and different OCT imaging modalities including intervolumetric speckle contrast are evaluated.

1. INTRODUCTION

Optical coherence tomography (OCT) as a non-invasive, three-dimensional imaging technique has a growing impact on diagnostics of skin diseases. For clinical application and with respect to bulk motion artifacts the image acquisition time is a crucial factor. With the development of multi-megahertz Fourier Domain Mode Locked (FDML) lasers, the imaging speed of the OCT systems was dramatically increased [1]. Besides high temporal resolution for live 3D imaging at video volume update rates [2], the high A-scan rate of our home-built 3.3 MHz-OCT system is also beneficial for large area scanning OCT using mosaicking [3].

In this work, we investigate several options to decrease the overall acquisition time for large area scanning OCT. We designed a motorized and controllable XYZ positioning stage for automated mosaicking OCT. A unique feature of the positioning stage is that the scan head of the OCT system is moved instead of the sample. This allows for higher flexibility and *in vivo* measurements of different body sites. Also, for *in vitro* samples in a liquid environment this technique is advantageous due to fewer sample motion artifacts. Further, different scanning protocols dedicated to efficient scanning are investigated for large field of view (FOV), intervolumetric intensity based vascular contrast [4], and high-resolution mosaicking OCT imaging. We demonstrate mosaicking MHz-OCT that potentially enables rapid acquisition of large areas with up to up to 1 cm²/sec imaging speed for investigation of e.g. extended skin lesions.

2. METHODS

All data shown here has been acquired using a home-built OCT system based on an FDML laser source with a center wavelength of 1310 nm and an effective A-scan rate of 3.3 MHz. We used a spectral bandwidth of ~100 nm, the incident power on the sample was 25 mW and OCT data were acquired at 4 GS/s with a sample depth of 12 bit (AlazarTech, ATS9373, Canada).

To raster-scan samples for 3D volumetric OCT imaging, the output beam of the optical fiber is collimated using an 18.4 mm aspheric lens and directed to a pair of galvanometer mirror scanners (Cambridge Technology, 6215H, USA) used in unidirectional scanning mode. For large area scanning, a 50 mm scan lens is used to focus the OCT beam onto the sample. For high-resolution imaging, 4f relay optics are used to enlarge the collimated beam diameter for optimal illumination of a 10x near infrared objective (Mitutoyo, M Plan Apo NIR 10x, Japan).

Mode	LFM	VCM	HRM
lateral FOV	11.9x11.9 mm	2.2x2.2 mm	1.4x1.4 mm
A-scans x frames	2048x2048	256x256	1024x1024
pixel spacing	5.8 μm/pix	8.9 μm/pix	1.4 μm/pix
lateral resolution	22.08 μm	24.81 μm	~ 4 μm
scanning frame rate	1.01 kHz	2.25 kHz	1.47 kHz
scanning duration	2.028 sec	0.111 sec	0.694 sec
acquisition time	1.258 sec	0.019 sec	0.315 sec

Table 1 Scanning protocols

Figure 1 Design of the positioning stage

A motorized XYZ positioning stage was designed for large area mosaicking OCT, shown in Figure 1. The combination of three linear stages allows a scan area of approximately 22.5x22.5x22.5 cm. For precise positioning, stepper motors (TRINAMIC Motion Control GmbH, QSH4218-51-10-049-10000-AT, Germany) and the corresponding triple axis stepper motor driver board (TRINAMIC Motion Control GmbH, TMCM-3110-TMCL, Germany) are used. A control software (LabVIEW, National Instruments, USA) was developed that allows for automated scan head positioning synchronized with our OCT imaging software.

Three different scanning protocols at fastest possible galvanometer scanning speed for different imaging purposes were elaborated: a large FOV mode (LFM), a vascular contrast mode (VCM) and a high-resolution mode (HRM) using the Mitutoyo objective. Detailed parameters for one volume scan of the three modes are depicted in Table 1. To test each mode, OCT images of the researcher's hand were acquired and evaluated. Vascular contrast is calculated by intervolumetric speckle contrast and therefore 5 volumes per position are acquired. For mosaicking, the motorized scan head is moved according to the specific lateral FOV of each mode. Following the OCT image processing, stitching was performed using the Microsoft Image Composite Editor. All *in vivo* experiments of human hands are conducted on voluntarily basis by experts of our group and approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Lübeck.

3. RESULTS

6x2 OCT volumes of a finger using the large FOV mode are displayed in Figure 2. A total area of 63.8x23.8 mm was acquired within ~4 minutes due to non-optimized software. The real effective acquisition time of the 60.398 GVoxels OCT data was 15.1 sec. Stitching was performed in two planes with 23 % overlap in each direction. In the B-scan views (Figure 2b, c) minor stitching artifacts are visible, but the enface projections appear seamless.

Figure 2 Large FOV 3.3 MHz OCT scan of a finger. (a) Stitched enface projection composed of 6x2 tiles. (b-c) Stitched B-scan views of the same dataset at the position of the color-coded dashed lines. For both images 10-fold averaging of adjacent B-scans was performed and afterwards stitched. (d) Photograph of the finger.

In Figure 3, stitched OCT images using vascular contrast and high-resolution mode are presented. For the HRM images, 5x5 tiles with 26 % stitching overlap resulting in a total area of 5.8x5x8 mm were acquired within 3.1 min. Stitching artifacts are most obvious in the B-scan views, but also present in the stitched enface projections, as well as vignetting artifacts. To test the VCM, 48 OCT volumes of the thenar with 5x repetition were acquired at a total acquisition time of 5 min. Subsequently, the enface projections, as well as the speckle contrast in different depths, were calculated, displayed in Figure 3f and g. The image quality of the contrast OCT image is affected by the tilt of the cover glass on top of the thenar and minor motion artifacts.

Figure 3 High-resolution and vascular contrast mosaicking MHz OCT images of a palm. (a-d) 5x5 stitched high-resolution OCT images of the fingertip. (a-c) Enface projections at different depths indicated by the green dashed lines in the B-scan view (d). (f-g) OCT of the thenar consisting of 8x6 volumes. (f) stitched intensity-based enface projections and (g) the corresponding stitched vascular contrast mode OCT image of the same dataset. (e) Photograph of the palm.

4. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The imaging experiments with the motorized stage show promising first results for ultra-large area mosaicking MHz-OCT. It allows for large FOV OCT imaging with minor stitching artifacts at an effective acquisition rate of 1 cm²/sec. Due to scanning and processing delays, the current overall imaging time for large area scanning is limited to 16 sec/cm². However, we estimate to bring this time down to less than 1 sec/cm² by optimizing data streaming, stage movement and implementing bidirectional scanning to reduce the overall acquisition dead time.

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